

The Dark Sides of Modern Science: The Curse

Taha Sochi (Contact: t.sochi@ucl.ac.uk)
London, United Kingdom

Abstract: This is the fifth article in our series “The Dark Sides of Modern Science” and is about the curse of science (and knowledge in general). The remarks that we stated in the Introduction of the first article of this series (i.e. “Knowledge Production and Authoring”) generally apply to this article and hence we do not need to repeat.

Keywords: Ethics of science, ethics of knowledge, morality in science, academic misconduct, corruption in science, corruption related to science.

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7 Torture

Also see “Human Experimentation” section (refer to § 2) in this article.

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59. Palestine: The Human Cost of Capitalist Exploitation.
60. Gaza, Ukraine, and the Moral Bankruptcy of the "Rules-Based Order".
61. Western moral credibility is dying along with thousands of Gaza citizens.
62. The Moral Bankruptcy of the West.
63. The war in Gaza has been an intense lesson in western hypocrisy. It won't be forgotten.
64. Nobel Laureates Who Were Not Always Noble.
65. U.S. Universities Must Stop Honoring Racist Scientists of the Past.
66. Richard Dawkins' latest anti-Muslim Twitter spat lays bare his hypocrisy.
67. Richard Dawkins Defends 'Mild' Pedophilia, Again and Again.
68. Scientists mobilise against 'weaponisation' of research.
69. Enslaved people's health was ignored from the country's beginning, laying the ground-

work for today's health disparities.

70. Academia is built on exploitation. We must break this vicious circle.
71. Sexual misconduct strikes at the heart of university life.
72. Revealed: how Israel offered to sell South Africa nuclear weapons.
73. Tracing A Link Between Science And Xenophobia.
74. Western philosophy is racist.
75. Weaponisation of Science.
76. How Academia Resembles a Drug Gang.
77. Let's stop pretending that science is apolitical.
78. International Convention Against War and Destructive Use of Science: Scientists Against Israeli Apartheid, Occupation and Genocide in Gaza.
79. The myth of white purity and narratives that fed racism in South Africa.
80. How Foucault was shielded from scandal by French reverence for intellectuals.
81. Michel Foucault: the prophet of pederasty.
82. French philosopher Michel Foucault 'abused boys in Tunisia'.
83. Paedophilia thesis comes under fire.
84. Schrodinger's Pedophilia: The Cat Is Out Of The Bag (Box).
85. Helmut Kentler.
86. D. Carleton Gajdusek dies at 85; Nobel Prize winner identified exotic disease, was unrepentant pedophile.
87. Matthew Falder: The scientist who was unmasked as one of Britain's most sadistic sex offenders.
88. South Pole paedophile Simon Rouen jailed.
89. Exposing pedophilia and legal failures in Israel.